

When purchasing coffee, we typically have three criteria that include taste, price and the final one that influences our decisions at a subconscious level is the popularity of coffee brands.

Today, the popularity of every brand. Certain brands may be poor with regards to their practices, however due to clever marketing, they're the brands that consumers purchase more from. There are also brands that you and I may not even know about but they offer excellent quality products with ethical and responsible business practices.

We've picked the most popular coffee brands in the globe which have existed for a long time that you may recognize.

1 Starbucks

Founded in 1971 at Seattle, Washington

Everyone is familiar with Starbucks because of their aggressive marketing strategy and clever advertising strategies. But, does everyone like Starbucks coffee? The answer varies.

The company is not well-known for its roasting and sourcing the finest coffee beans. The majority of their coffee beans are dark roasted that is, they taste bitter. There are many customers who know their coffee are unhappy that Starbucks coffee has a distinct burnt flavor.

That's okay for the company. They know what typical consumer likes - caffeine. Their coffees are also infused with an abundance of caffeine. Additionally, Starbucks keeps coming up with new blends and modified versions that include their coffee. With frequent tasting panels that the business understands exactly how much tweaking requires to reach the common consumer.

Additionally, Starbucks gives you a range of coffees to pick from. According to official sources, they do offer premium coffees, but this might not be the kind you receive every day.

In addition it, the company is working to become more environmentally friendly. They are offering more meals that are made from plants and removing single-use cups, and attempting to reduce their waste better and...let's believe that this is the start of something truly extraordinary.

2 Dunkin' Doughnuts

Founded in 1950 at Canton, Massachusetts

Dunkin' isn't as popular an organization as Starbucks however, they're second in in the quantity of stores. The Dunkin's coffee Dunkin' offers is surely more superior than Starbucks. In particular, Dunkin' does not have the signature burnt flavor in the coffee that Starbucks does. It also costs less.

The major distinction between these two companies is the fact that Dunkin' is more of an old-fashioned eatery, whereas Starbucks is a top coffee shop that allows customers to customize and select from a wide menu.

The great thing about Dunkin' Dunkin' is that you can get free doughnuts every now and then.

3 Costa Coffee

Founded in 1971 at London, United Kingdom

Costa coffee is among the biggest chain of coffee shops in Britain. With its presence throughout more than 31 different countries and more than 3000 locations serving coffee and has around 18000 branches across the world.

Costa coffees are medium-roasted and are more smooth, sweeter and more nutty.

4 McCafe

Founded in 1993 at Melbourne, Australia

As a subsidiary of McDonald's, McCafe is one of the top coffee chains in countries such as Australia in addition to New Zealand. McCafe has the advantage of having a large presence (Because there's no doubt that McDonald's has a presence everywhere!) When McDonald's expands its reach across the globe and expands its reach, there's a good possibility of McCafe making the same move.

The coffee, however, is freshly made each 30 min, meaning it's never old. Although it's medium-roasted, it does have an unpleasant taste, but it also offers a variety of flavours to pair to the coffee.

The more light roast coffee, the better flavorful it will be. If you're drinking coffee at McCafe you can expect to taste the bitter aftertaste of nutty.

Apart from that, the coffees are also cheap.

5 Peet's Coffee

Founded in 1966 at California, United States

Peet's coffee is believed to be a bit more robust in comparison to the espresso Starbucks serves, so it may not be suitable for all. Peet's has an extensive history of serving darker-roasted Arabica coffee. The coffee is believed to come in various flavors .

If you're one who is unable to endure the bitter taste of coffee, you might appreciate Peet's. Additionally, the layout of the store is classic and the company keeps a [Coffee Primary Blog](#) positive connection with its supply chain (aka farmers).

6 Nescafe

Founded in 1938 at Switzerland

If there's another coffee that is widely known that is Nescafe. It's available virtually everywhere in the world. Instant coffee made by Nescafe is unbeatable, but not just for taste, but it is in terms of accessibility.

In terms of taste It's not the most flavorful instant coffee. In addition, the instant sensation of rejuvenation you feel after drinking a cup of Nescafe can disappear after a few hours.

One of the major reason why Nescafe is so well-known is due to its hosting company Nestle. Nestle utilized its vast pockets and smart marketing to make Nescafe all over the globe. The importance of distribution support is in the world of coffee!

7 Bru Coffee

Launched in 1968 at India

Originating from India, Bru is perhaps one of the biggest competitors to Nescafe in South Asia. It isn't all coffee however, it's a beautiful blend of chicory and coffee.

With its authentic flavor and the regular release of new instant coffees, Bru deserves to be in our the top 10.

8 Gloria Jean's Coffees

Founded in 1979 at Australia

Gloria Jean's definitely has an increased presence in Australia with over 350 outlets. However, this doesn't mean that it's not doing well in the world also. There are around 1000 stores across the world and Bangladesh is among them.

Regarding the coffee, it's decent quality coffee but nothing you'd be able to keep for long.

9 Tim Horton's

Founded in 1964 in Ontario, Canada

As one of the most storied coffee brands Tim Horton's cafes are the more traditional ambience. It's fast-food chain, with more limited coffee options.

This is the reason the reason why people are so in love with the establishment. If you're an individual who enjoys coffee with just sugar and cream, then you'll be awed by the Tim Horton's coffee shop has to provide.

And, they also sell doughnuts!

10 Folgers

Introduced in 1850 at the United States

Folgers is among the most famous brand of coffee across the United States. The brand is famous for their ground coffee , and it is believed to have revolutionized the concept of it in addition.

The coffee isn't exceptional in flavor, perhaps even mediocre. If brewed correctly you can enjoy moderate cups of coffee. If you are unable to buy anything else it's not good in any way.

But you should know that there's more to it:

There it was the list. Let's discuss the options that are more sustainable. Are you aware of what makes a brand successful? Is it simply the brand's popularity or what the brand truly represents?

Many of the brands that are successful are, unfortunately, concerned too little about the people who work for them and farmers, or even about a fair and minimal wages. Certain of them could be more concerned about the world's environment and all its inhabitants.

However, the positive side is that certain brands are on completely different. They're sustainable, ingenious and can amaze you!

Larry's Coffee

Larry's is among the most unique brands there. Their organic, shade-grown coffee is delicious and doesn't taste bland. If there's one thing that stands out is the way they do business.

With their solar-powered water heated floors, rainwater-driven restrooms, natural lighting zones, zone heating composting, rainwater harvesting the possibility of growing edible gardens at their roastery, and more, they're one of the top fair-trade, sustainable coffee companies available! Also, they are affordable.

They offer their beverages in completely compostable BPA no-cost cups!

Cafe Mam

A genuine, shade-grown coffee company that gives their time to the community. Their coffee is organically certified and they also offer decaffeinated coffees to select from!

The coffee is available in compostable and recyclable packaging, and the company is committed to sustainable development.

Ethical Bean

Are you curious about what the origins of your coffee are? Then, with Ethical Bean, you can actually trace the origin of your coffee and find out more about it!

The coffee offered by the brand is sourced seasonally and tastes delicious. They also use a fair trade model of business and the costs of production are covered by the purchase.

There's plenty others to mention: Equal Exchange, Salt Spring, Conscious Coffees, Grumpy Mule, Cafe Direct They are among the few brands that are sustainable available that are more concerned than profit.

We hope that you enjoyed this list, and perhaps it's time to discover more about coffee, it is not necessary to be a coffee connoisseur in order to accomplish that.